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Review of Theories and Studies on the Characteristics of Safety Culture

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ABSTRACT

The concept of "safety culture" is notoriously nebulous! Over the last 30 years, researchers have proposed a wide range of definitions, ranging from simple ones, such as "the way we improve operations without sacrificing worker safety," to complex ones, such as "what people at all levels of an organization do and say when their commitment to safety is not being scrutinized." A robust safety culture is commonly seen as a prerequisite for a well-functioning safety management system; this implies that one cannot have an effective safety management system (policies, procedures, formal plans, dealing with risk and safety-related information) without a safety culture (shared values, beliefs, and attitudes regarding safety, etc.). Across all industries, cultivating a positive safety culture is becoming a major responsibility. This paper looks at what it takes to have a good safety culture and why it is so important.

1. INTRODUCTION

According to the International Labour Organization (ILO), approximately 2.3 million women and men die each year as a result of work-related accidents or diseases; this equates to over 6,000 deaths per day. Every year, there are approximately 340 million occupational accidents and 160 million victims of work-related diseases worldwide. The ILO updates these estimates at regular intervals, and the updates show an increase in accidents and diseases. Over 11,000 fatal occupational accidents are estimated to have occurred in the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) countries, compared to 5,850 reported cases (information lacking from 2 countries). Gross underreporting of work-related accidents, diseases and deaths, gives a false picture of how big the problem is.

Below are some of the most important things that the ILO's most recent statistics on accidents, diseases and deaths at work around the world have shown:

- Work-related diseases are the leading cause of death among workers. Every year, hazardous substances are estimated to kill 651,279 people.
- Accidents in the construction industry are disproportionately common.

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- Workers, both young and old, are particularly vulnerable. Because developed countries' populations are aging, an increasing number of older people are working and require special consideration.

Since 1996, the ILO has designated April 28 as World Day for Safety and Health at Work, a day to focus the attention of the world's governments, workers, and employers on a common agenda centered on reducing suffering through preventative measures. The ability to address the causes and stop the suffering is the unifying theme. Fortunately, an increasing number of companies are proving that safer, healthier workplaces can be created via collaboration and communication between employees, employers, and governments. This is the new trend of encouraging a "safety culture" at work.

According to the ILO, a safe culture necessitates three essential commitments:

- A commitment from businesses to implement occupational health and safety management systems.
- A commitment to worker participation and involvement in such systems.
- A commitment to create a global framework so that local action on safety and health is not undermined by erroneous competitiveness concerns.

These pledges are based on the ILO's real-world experience working with its tripartite partners – governments, workers, and employers – to solve the most pressing challenges pertaining to workplace safety and health. It is evident that businesses with an occupational safety and health system developed in accordance with ILO recommendations perform better in terms of both safety and productivity. Modern managers are aware that worker input is a valuable resource for enhancing workplace safety, productivity, and competitiveness. Historical evidence demonstrates that strong and effective union representation results in safer workplaces. In Sweden, for example, high safety standards are a direct result of worker participation laws and practices that have been in place for a long period of time and a tripartite system that works well.

This paper examines what creating a positive safety culture entails and why it is so vital. It provides an exemplary literature review. What is meant by an exemplary literature review? A literature review can be divided into two categories: exemplary and exhaustive. It has been noted that "in the exemplary review, the writer assumes the reader knows about the subject and so presents only key references to reacquaint the reader with representative works that relate to the research study". On the other hand, an exhaustive literature review is thought to be complete because the author looks up and presents all of the information about the research area (Rubin et al., 2009, p.236).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The purpose of the literature review was to examine the scientific literature pertaining to the value of safety and safety as a value. Safety can be an asset for organizations, individuals (such as managers and employees), and society as a whole. Other than economic worth, there are very few peer-reviewed scientific articles on the value of safety. In fact, the value of safety and safety values are implicit in the majority of safety research (as the objective is often to contribute in some way to the enhancement of safety). However, it is rarely directly addressed in scholarly publications (Ratilainen R., 2016).

Internationally, the importance of safety and safety values is gaining prominence. The International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA, 2009) was perhaps the first international body to declare that "safety should be a clearly an acknowledged value." "Safety as a fundamental value" is a requirement of the most recent European Guidelines for offshore operations of the oil and gas industry.

The phrase "safety is our value" is also frequently utilized by industry leaders and consultants (Ratilainen R., 2016). Many businesses state that safety is their top priority, but does this imply that safety is a (fundamental) value? Values are the guiding concepts or principles that govern an organization's internal behavior and its interactions with the outside world. People are guided by their values as to what is good or desirable and what is not. This shows that values are more stable and likely to have a longer-lasting effect on safety than "priorities."

Many businesses nowadays have articulated their basic principles; these serve to define and cultivate their "business identity." In the management literature, the influence of shared core values is frequently discussed. According to McKinsey's well-known 7S framework, shared values influence an organization's structure, strategy, systems, style, skills, and personnel.

In recent years, safety research has increasingly accepted that (value-based) management commitment and an economic viewpoint are vital for safety performance. However, little research has been conducted on the value of safety; there is confusion on the definition and impact of safety values, and there are no evidence-based techniques to support, promote, and disseminate safety values.

One can assert that safety has an intrinsic value (Zwetsloot G. et al., 2013). There are many grounds to believe that workplace safety has inherent value. Certainly, "what the majority of people consider to be vital in life" includes safety (a definition of value). However, this does not provide us with a definition of the value of safety or safety values.

There are various interpretations of the concept of safety culture in the literature, with perhaps the most significant difference being between authors who see safety culture as something that an organization has or does not have, and others who see safety culture as the intersection of the organization's culture (something that all organizations develop over time) and safety culture. In this latter interpretation, it is important to note that organizational culture may serve as a reservoir of tacit knowledge on safe ways of working, act as a soft coordination mechanism, and encourage people to maintain a questioning attitude, challenging beliefs and practices, and increasing imagination about possible accident scenarios. It may also shield members of an organization from opposing views, penalize deviation from group norms, and perpetuate myths that foster the illusion of control (Clarke, 1993). Several papers on safety culture have been published in the World Safety Journal, such as: Lal H., 2022; Lal H., 2021; Baylee S., Brazilie B. & Gilkey D., 2020; Marais W. & Jansz J., 2019a; Marais W. & Jansz J., 2019b; Gilkey D. & Lopez C., 2018; Yu S., 2018; Cervantes M., 2017; Bo W., 2017; Chiri K. & Jansz J., 2016; and Yu S., 2016).

One complete definition of safety culture comes from the HSC's Advisory Committee on the Safety of Nuclear Installations (ACSNI, 1993).

'The safety culture of an organisation is the product of individual and group values, attitudes, perceptions, competencies, and patterns of behaviour that determine the commitment to, and the style and proficiency of, an organisation's health and safety management. Organisations with a positive safety culture are characterised by communication founded on mutual trust, by shared perceptions of the importance of safety and by confidence in the efficacy of preventive measures.'

According to Marsden (2021), a "safety culture" is an organizational culture that provides safety concepts, values and attitudes, a high level of importance that is shared by most employees or workers. Organizational culture can be thought of as consisting of three interrelated levels, as shown in Figure 1 below (Schein, 1985). As Figure 1 reveals, the "deepest" level of an organization's culture is made up of its fundamental assumptions and beliefs: what people value; what contributes to performance; what performance means; and the stories members tell newcomers to the organization. These are intangible, tacit (not written or verbalized), and unspoken attitudes and beliefs. The second level consists of values, shared principles, rituals, behavioral standards, and goals. It also includes public statements about the organization's values and rules of conduct (how the members represent the organization to themselves and to others). Lastly, the "surface" level includes artifacts, the physical environment, interaction mechanisms, official policies, the dress code, and other visible parts of how people in the organization interact with each other (Schein, 1985).

Figure 1. Schein's "onion layer" model of organizational culture (Schein, 1985)

Organizational culture is something that an organization is not something that can be changed quickly or easily (gothamCulture). Subcultures that differ from the dominant organizational culture are commonly found in large organizations. Subcultures form within organizations when members with similar identities or job functions band together to form their own interpretations of the organizational culture. Edgar Schein, an organizational theorist, identified three subcultures that exist in many organizations: executives, whose primary concern is financial performance; engineers, who solve problems using technology and specialized knowledge; and operators, who run the organization's systems. Within complex organizations, there are frequently much narrower subcultures based on age, occupation, seniority, shift, and previous occupation (Mearns et al., 1998).

3. SAFETY CULTURE DIMENSIONS

According to Reason (1990), safety culture has several dimensions, which are depicted in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2. Dimensions of safety culture (Reason, 1990)

Turner (1992) identified four dimensions of a "good" safety culture:

- the development of a compassionate organizational response to the consequences of actions and policies.
- a commitment at all levels, particularly the most senior, as well as an avoidance of overly stringent safety attitudes.
- feedback to practitioners from incidents within the system.
- the development of comprehensive and widely accepted rules and norms for dealing with safety issues, supported in a flexible and non-punitive manner.

According to Pidgeon and O'Leary (2000), a "good" safety culture may reflect and be promoted by four dimensions:

- senior management's commitment to safety.
- realistic and adaptable practices and customs for dealing with both well-defined and ill-defined hazards.
- continuous organizational learning through practices such as operational experience feedback.
- concern for hazards are shared throughout the workforce.

These attempts to break down the idea of safety culture into a small number of easy-to-understand (and maybe even measure) dimensions are appealing, but it should be noted that there is not much evidence that these dimensions cover the same things as Reason's (1990) broader concept.

4. ASSESSMENT OF SAFETY CULTURE

Safety culture can be "assessed" (defined along several dimensions) using a variety of methods, including questionnaires, interviews, focus groups, and observations (Eeckelaert et al. 2011). In the real world, quantitative questionnaires are the easiest and least expensive way to evaluate people; they are also the most popular method used in business.

There are numerous questionnaires available on the market. They cover the following dimensions:

- Priority, commitment, and competence in management safety.
- Management empowerment for safety.
- Justice for management safety.
- Workers' dedication to safety.
- Workers' safety and risk rejection.
- Communication about safety, learning about safety, and trust in coworkers' safety competence.
- Belief in the effectiveness of safety systems.

It should be noted that assessments based on surveys are prone to severe biases. When filling out surveys, people often give answers that they believe to be socially desirable rather than those that accurately reflect their true beliefs or attitudes. Worries about repercussions ("would our unit be punished if our results were bad?") for poor survey performance can also discourage participation in safety culture surveys. In addition, people are sensitive to the prevailing social atmosphere. Also, when morale is low, survey limitations become clearer because people are less likely to say what they really think about the company's culture out of fear of getting in trouble.

5. ORGANIZATIONAL FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE THE HEALTH AND SAFETY CULTURE

A number of organizational factors have been found to influence the health and safety culture of an organization and are also associated with good safety performance. According to the ILO, the key ones are:

- Effective communication requires a high level of communication between and within organizational levels, as well as comprehensive formal and informal communications.
- The learning organization must constantly improve its methods and learn from its errors.
- A strong focus on health and safety by everyone in the organization on health and safety is a must.
- Pressures from outside the organization, such as the organization's financial status and the impact of regulatory bodies, must be taken seriously.
- Time, money, and personnel devoted to health and safety are strong indicators of dedication.
- Employees at all levels of the organization must identify hazards, propose control measures, provide feedback, and establish safety procedures.
- Senior executives must demonstrate a strong commitment to safety.
- The need for productivity must be properly balanced with the need for health and safety, so that the latter are not overlooked.
- High-quality training must be well managed, with well-chosen content and high quality. Counting the hours spent on training is insufficient.
- A clean and comfortable work environment is required, including general cleanliness, plant layout, etc.

- Safety, trust, and recognition of the impact of good safety performance, must be regarded.
- The composition of the labor force must be taken into account. For instance, studies have shown that a significant proportion of older, more experienced, and socially stable workers have fewer accidents, lower absenteeism, and lower turnover.

The HSE has suggested that the following components be included in an organization's management system (Health & Safety, 2022):

- Top-down commitment to creating a safe environment in which management's goals and the need for appropriate standards are openly discussed, and the free flow of information is actively supported at all levels.
- Incident investigation and making good use of data gathered from those probes must be implemented to achieve this goal. Furthermore, adequate and effective supervision is required to address deficiencies as they arise.

6. ORGANIZATIONAL FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH A CULTURE OF SAFETY AND HEALTH

The foundation of good health and a safety culture is an effective health and safety management system. Certain key aspects of an organization's culture influence it. According to the ILO, these factors are often intangible and difficult to change or incorporate:

- The commitment of senior management is critical for fostering a positive health and safety culture. This commitment instills a sense of urgency and concern for health and safety throughout the organization. The proportion of resources (time, money, and people) and support dedicated to health and safety management, as well as the status accorded to health and safety, best demonstrate this. Senior management's active participation in the health and safety system is critical. Managers must lead by example in terms of health and safety.
- Effective management style. A 'humanistic' management approach in which managers pay more attention to individuals' personal and professional problems is likely to be effective. This requires prompt and direct action to identify and resolve individual problems in a caring and concerned manner.
- Visible management is essential for fostering a health and safety culture. Good managers must visit the "shop floor" frequently to discuss health and safety. Employees must have confidence that all of their managers care about their health and safety.
- Effective communication at all organizational levels. An "open door" policy with direct access to the management hierarchy may be advantageous where appropriate. In a positive culture, questions about health and safety should be part of everyday work conversations. This stems from ownership, which encourages everyone to look after themselves and contribute to health and safety measures.
- A balance of health, safety, and productivity goals. People may mistakenly believe that high health and safety standards necessitate slower work rates. In contrast, production may appear to be increased by 'cutting corners.' Excessive production pressure creates a distraction-filled environment with a lack of time, which increases the likelihood of human error. Excessive pressure can lead to physical or mental health issues in some employees, as well as an increase

in 'violations' of health and safety regulations. Health and safety are valued, promoted, and not jeopardized in a positive culture.

To help alleviate organizational issues that are associated with a culture of safety and health, the Health and Safety Commission (HSC) issued recommendations for board members to follow (Health & Safety, 2022). According to HSC, each board member individually and the Board as a whole are responsible for setting a tone of leadership in terms of health and safety. If the Board is serious about improving health and safety, it must make that aim clear in all of its actions and involve employees in those efforts. In addition, the Board must remain abreast of developing health and safety concerns. Further, the Board's efforts to improve health and safety will be viewed as clear indicators of their commitment.

7. THE TOP 10 SAFETY CULTURE CONCERNS

7.1 What does safety culture entail?

All of the attitudes, practices, and beliefs about safety that exist in any establishment are referred to as the "safety culture". The atmosphere created by those attitudes, beliefs, etc., can be defined as the company's culture.

Safety culture affects how employees act and is caused by a number of things, such as:

- Employee and management norms, beliefs, and assumptions;
- Employee and management attitudes;
- Values, myths, and stories;
- Policies and procedures;
- Responsibilities, priorities, and accountability of supervisors;
- Inaction or actions taken to correct risky behavior;
- Bottom-line and production demands vs. quality concerns;
- Employee involvement, or "buy in"; and
- Motivation and employee training.

7.2 Are employees at ease asking questions about safety?

If employees are hesitant to ask safety-related questions or are afraid of being disciplined for raising safety concerns, it is very likely that someone will be injured by one of those uncorrected hazards.

The most effective organizations have open lines of communication, and management is always willing to address safety concerns.

7.3 Are employees from one trade comfortable approaching someone from another trade in an emergency?

Simply put, no one enjoys being questioned, especially by someone from a different trade. "Who are you to tell me how to do my job properly?" is the most common response.

However, in the most positive environment, employees from various departments feel free to offer advice to those from other departments in order to prevent injuries.

7.4 Is it mandatory for employees to report close calls and incidents?

Employees in environments with a healthy safety culture are always looking for new ways to improve safety, which necessitates learning from close calls. If these incidents are dismissed or ignored, there is a much lower chance that a more tragic event will occur in the future.

One of the most important questions about safety culture is whether or not your employees are encouraged to report close calls and incidents.

7.5 How are hazardous conditions addressed?

It is critical that all reports of unsafe conditions be corrected as soon as possible. If not, it communicates to employees that their safety is not valued.

When hazards are promptly corrected, employees feel valued and are more likely to report similar incidents in the future.

7.6 Can your employees refuse to work in potentially hazardous conditions?

The safest workplaces are those in which management trusts employees enough to make decisions about their own safety.

Simply put, if a worker considers an area unsafe to work in, they should not be required to do so. It conveys the organization's trust and respect for each employee.

7.7 How involved are managers in the safety process?

Supervisors should discuss safety at every meeting and walk around the site to identify problems as soon as possible. Simply put, managers should not only talk the talk, but also walk the walk.

It will be even more difficult to persuade workers of the importance of safety if it is not discussed on every walk-around and at every meeting. Supervisors must set a good example.

7.8 Is the company offering any incentives to discourage incident reporting?

While everyone loves incentives, programs that discourage employees from reporting any type of safety incident can completely undermine the safety culture.

Because no employee wants to be blamed for not receiving an incentive, it is critical to carefully craft programs. They must be designed in such a way that they do not discourage incident reporting.

7.9 Are employees stressed and prone to taking shortcuts?

Most projects are under severe budget and time constraints, which may lead to employees seeking shortcuts. Better planning that includes safety provisions is one way to alleviate these pressures.

7.10 Is the management team attentive?

Supervisors must be active listeners as well as active participants in all safety programs. They must actively consider suggestions for improvement and never dismiss them.

Most of the time, employees will have the best ideas because they are on the ground and are likely to know where the problems are.

8. THE ROLE OF SAFETY CULTURE: AN INTERVIEW WITH AN HSE EXECUTIVE

Prior to the MENA HSE Forum, which was held in Dubai on September 6-7, 2022, the head of HSE at Kuwait Energy Egypt, Wael Amin, emphasized the significance of developing an effective safety culture (HSSR, 2022). Below are the interview's Q&A.

Q. What is safety culture?

A. Modern conceptions of safety culture vary widely. The majority of them are based on the definition provided by the Advisory Committee on Safety from the 1980s, which states that it is "the product of individual and group values, attitudes, competencies, perceptions, and behavioral patterns that determine the commitment to, and the style and proficiency of an organization's health and safety management."

OSHA defines safety culture as "shared beliefs, practices, and attitudes that exist at a workplace." Culture is the environment created by the beliefs, attitudes, and so on that shape our behavior. The following are some of the advantages of a strong safety culture:

- Creating a strong safety culture has the greatest single impact on accident reduction of any process.
- A company with a strong safety culture has fewer risky behaviors, lower accident rates, lower turnover, lower absenteeism, and higher productivity.
- Building a stronger safety culture benefits not only safety, but also productivity, staff retention, and the overall organizational culture.
- It is critical to understand that effective consequences for behaviors and performance are required for successful world-class safety cultures.

Q. How crucial is it to establish a successful safety culture?

A. In order to understand the significance of a safety culture in the workplace, we should first notice the following: According to the International Labor Organization (ILO), workplace accidents and illnesses account for 2.3 million deaths worldwide each year. That translates to 13 fatalities per 100,000 workers globally. The rate ranges from 0.5 to 3.5 deaths per 100,000 workers in wealthy nations, but it climbs rapidly to about 19 deaths per 100,000 workers in rising economies like sub-Saharan Africa, Latin America, and southern Asia. In addition to the human tragedy, workplace accidents cost the economy roughly 4% of GDP. Before the Health and Safety at Work Act was implemented in the UK in 1974, there were typically 650 fatal workplace accidents per year. By 2016/2017, there were 137 fewer fatalities, or less than one-fourth of that number.

High standards are set for all safety procedures thanks to a strong safety culture. The organization has tight procedures for reporting, inspecting, training, and general safety management. A "safety culture" is an organizational culture that gives safety concepts, values, and attitudes a high level of importance and that is shared by most employees or workers. You could say it is "the way we do things around here."

Q. What steps would you take to create a strong safety culture, and what conditions must be met for success?

- Make safety a core value, not just a top concern. The guiding principles should be a part of everyday life.
- Strong management commitment entails fast and attentive engagement in all layers (layered safety interactions), making the safety management system (SMS) more than just a formal procedure to prove legal compliance. At every level of business, people work together to achieve the same production-related goals and ideals.
- Empowering people to successfully meet their safety responsibilities to their families, coworkers, and themselves.
- Communication: Make sure there is top-down and bottom-up feedback and two-way communication.
- Ongoing improvement: Have we improved since yesterday?

Q. What are the biggest obstacles to establishing and preserving a strong safety culture?

- Safety is viewed as more of a barrier than a value, and profit is the major priority.
- Autocratic and oppressive management.
- A culture of punishment has resulted in a lack of trust.
- Insufficient reporting, with few events, concerns, or near-misses reported.
- Ineffective work monitoring and evaluation; failure to employ performance indicators, audit results, and incident reporting for study of safety management system's efficacy and organizational learning.
- The inability of managers at all levels to effectively manage risk.

Q. How do safety culture and the safety management system relate to one another?

A. A well-functioning safety management system is typically thought to require a strong safety culture. This indicates that without a safety culture (common values, beliefs, and attitudes about safety, etc.) in place, it is impossible to create an effective safety management system (policies, procedures, formal plans, dealing with risk and safety-related information).

9. CONCLUSION

Clearly, the influence of organizational cultural features on safety performance is an important area of research. Unfortunately, rather than seeking to appreciate current studies on organizational culture, a great deal of attention has been paid to a different set of theorized traits known as the "safety culture". Creating and sustaining a healthy safety culture is a significant and complex task. Safety must be ingrained in every individual, regardless of rank, for a successful safety culture to exist.

Several safety-related values are essential for promoting or establishing safety practices and/or a safety culture. Justice (Dekker, 2007; Reason, 1997), trust, and knowledge (Reason, 1997) are the most well-

known. Trust between managers and employees, and a just culture appear to be prerequisites for the propagation of safety values.

The relationship between safety values and company culture is close. However, safety culture is a broader notion (with multiple meanings) that encompasses values, norms, attitudes, practices, and principles connected to safety.

A strong safety culture ensures that all safety processes comply with stringent regulations. Commonly, a strong safety culture is seen as a necessity for an effective safety management system. This means that a safety culture (shared values, beliefs, and attitudes about safety, etc.) is needed for a safety management system (policies, procedures, and formal plans that deal with risk and safety-related information) to work.

According to the literature review, any safety program or culture depends on a strong safety leadership. There is nothing directing the program to success without solid leadership. Every leader must follow these seven guidelines in order to "walk the walk" when it comes to safety:

- **Vision.** In order to communicate safety excellence throughout the business, leaders must be able to "see" what it looks like.
- **Collaboration.** Effective leaders have good interpersonal skills, foster teamwork and collaboration, aggressively seek out the opinions of others on matters that concern them, and motivate their followers to carry out their decisions to increase safety.
- **Credibility.** Do the followers of the leader exhibit a great degree of trust? This means that everyone, from management to front-line workers, needs to be willing to take responsibility for mistakes and promote safety.
- **Communication.** Every time a safety leader speaks, they need to address safety. They must always speak from the perspective of safety.
- **A focus on action.** Is the safety leader prepared to take a proactive approach to safety rather than merely responding to incidents? Even in the absence of events, safety leaders need to act with haste to demonstrate their commitment to getting results.
- **Feedback and acclaim.** To help them assure consistency between their love for people and the message employees perceive based on their actions, leaders require honest and accurate feedback on the impact of their behaviors.
- **Accountability.** Any good leader promotes the idea that everyone in the organization is responsible for keeping things safe by giving workers an honest assessment of their safety efforts and results.

All of these factors come together to produce a culture that is both exemplary in terms of safety and conducive to workers wanting to do their jobs safely. In this endeavor, leaders in top-tier safety organizations can act as role models. Everything begins with a personal commitment to putting employees first, not last.

In conclusion, an organization's health and safety culture is an important factor in achieving and maintaining good health and safety performance. Open communication, management's commitment and leadership, the availability of resources, and balancing production goals with health and safety goals are all important parts of creating a positive culture.

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